

Unusual Presentation of Scarlet Fever with Staphylococcal Abscess- A Case Report

Mohnish Sekar^{1*}, Kavya R M²

¹Department of Dermatology, Karpaga Vinayaga Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, Tamilnadu, India

²Department of Dermatology, Chettinad Academy of Research and Education (Deemed to be University), Chettinad Health City, Rajiv Gandhi Salai (OMR) Kelambakkam, Tamilnadu, India

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***Corresponding author:** Mohnish Sekar, Department of Dermatology, Karpaga Vinayaga Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, Tamilnadu, India

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ABSTRACT

Scarlet fever is a bacterial infection characterized by a high temperature and exanthem of acute onset, typically with pharyngitis, and might cause severe complications. We present a case of scarlet fever with sandpaper rash, strawberry tongue, along with an unusual concomitant gluteal abscess. Growth of *Streptococcus pyogenes* was isolated from a throat swab, and staphylococcus aureus was obtained from the gluteal abscess during the evaluation. Patient improved with appropriate treatment without untoward sequelae.

Keywords: Scarlet fever; Sandpaper rash; Strawberry tongue; Scaly rash

INTRODUCTION

Scarlet fever, also called scarlatina, is caused by group A beta-hemolytic streptococcus (GABS), mainly transmitted through nasal droplet or direct contact with the skin or secretions of infected patients^[1]. Most cases occur in children aged 5–15 years of age with a seasonal predilection for winter and spring^[2]. The prevalence and morbidity associated with scarlet fever have decreased due to the advent of antibiotics. We present one such patient of scarlet fever, along with a concomitant gluteal abscess from our practice. We have also attempted to explain all the clinical features, including atypical presentations in brief.

CASE REPORT

A 9-year-old boy presented with a widespread scaly rash with a brush-like texture on the touch associated with itching. The rash initially started over the ears and progressed to the trunk, groin and extremities for two days, along with a history of fever, sore throat, cough, and cold for seven days. The patient also complained of painful swelling over the gluteal region for four days, with a history of applying turmeric and Kumkum on their own, which is a common practice in South India among rural population. There was no history of atopy. Examination

revealed a generalized pinhead-sized, skin-coloured papular exanthem with desquamation, rough in texture present over the ear lobules, neck, trunk, upper extremities, groin, and perineum (Figure 1). There was also a fluctuant abscess 4x3cm with few pustules and discolouration over the surface due to the application of condiments over the left gluteal region (Figure 2). An increase in temperature and tenderness was elicited on palpation. A general physical examination revealed a temperature of 101°C. Mucosal examination revealed papillar hypertrophy over the dorsum of the tongue, suggestive of strawberry tongue, and mucosal erythema over the buccal mucosa, palatoglossal arch and pharyngeal wall (Figure 3). Investigations revealed leucocytosis with neutrophilia and raised ESR. Throat culture was positive for streptococcus pyogenes. Incision and drainage of the gluteal abscess was done, and purulent material was subjected to culture and sensitivity, which showed the growth of Staphylococcus aureus. The patient was treated with oral amoxicillin-clavulanate for one week, along with conservative management of itching, fever and pain with antihistamines, antipyretic and analgesics resulting in resolution of symptoms in 7 days.

Figure 1: Diffuse skin coloured pinhead sized papular exanthem over trunk, upper extremity and groin.

Figure 2: Abscess over gluteal region.

Figure 3: Strawberry tongue

DISCUSSION

GABS, with its distinctive adaptation to the human body, it primarily inhabits the pharynx and saliva. Scarlet fever caused by *Streptococcus pyogenes* is transmitted mainly through nasal droplets and direct contact with the saliva of infected patients. It may also arise from streptococcal wound infections or burns^[3]. Scarlet fever is linked to the exotoxin genes Ssa, SpeA, and SpeC. It is caused by a small number of *Streptococcus pyogenes* lineages that are part of group A hemolytic *Streptococcus* (GAS)^[4]. Recent research suggests that there may be an association between scarlet fever and the opportunistic bacteria *Streptococcus sanguis*^[5]. The incubation period of scarlet fever ranges from 2 to 7 days. Scarlet fever is usually accompanied by acute pharyngitis presenting with hyperemia of the pharynx with early pin-point enanthema on the soft palate and enlarged and inflamed tonsils (with or without purulent exudates) with accompanying white strawberry tongue that turns red in the next couple of days after losing its covering resembling a red strawberry^[6]. A papular exanthem, which spreads cephalocaudally, follows the pharyngeal symptoms in 1-2 days. The skin is typically rough and abrasive due to the exanthem, which is prominent at the flexures. The rash subsides with palmoplantar peeling and branny desquamation in about two weeks^[7].

Superantigens secreted by GAS stimulates the immune system, causing an exaggerated hypersensitivity reaction which results in the distinctive clinical features observed in the scarlet fever^[3]. **Table 1** enumerates the clinical features and their characteristics^[6-9]

Clinical features	Strawberry tongue	Exanthem	Pastia's lines	Circumoral pallor
Other names	Raspberry tongue	Sandpaper rash (Because of the rough sensation of the skin caused by the raised bumps)	Thompson's sign	Filatov's mask

		<p>“sunburn with goose pimples,”</p> <p>“boiled-lobster” appearance</p>		
Appears on	1-2days after infection	3-4 days of the infection	3-4days (seen in severe cases)	-
Sites	Dorsum of tongue	Cephalocaudal spread	Skin folds in the neck, axillae, cubital fossae, groin and knees	The rash usually spares the face with reddish discoloration of the cheeks and a pallor around the eyes and mouth
Cause	Desquamation of the keratinized epithelium of the filiform papillae gives a red and denuded appearance mimicking the surface of a strawberry. This is intermixed with persistent, inflammatory, and	delayed-type hypersensitivity to an exotoxin	Capillary fragility	unknown

	<p>hypertrophic fungiform papillae (strawberry seeds).</p> <p>The tongue initially appears like a “white strawberry” because of the white covering that covers the hypertrophied papillae. After a few days, this covering desquamates, resulting in the classic “red strawberry” tongue.</p>			
variants	<p>1. Miliary (as 1 mm vesicles with whitish-yellowish exudate)</p> <p>2. Papular (on knees and elbows mainly), (usually seen simultaneously with typical sandpaper lesions)</p>	-	<p>Pastia lines are a hemorrhagic variant of exanthema, representing the severity of the condition.</p>	-
Atypical presentation	<p>smooth macular rash, exanthema</p>	-	-	-

	<p>over the palmoplantar surface; erythema and swelling of ear lobes, extensive erythroderma, localized facial erythroderma with coarse exanthema in the rest of the body; swelling involving eyelids, face, or the distal extremities, perianal dermatitis; and urticarial lesions</p>			
Resolution	-	<p>Characteristic resolution of the rash with characteristic branny desquamation and lamellar (plate-like) peeling of the palmar and plantar aspect of extremities</p>	-	-

High fever and evident systemic toxicity are the hallmarks of severe forms of scarlet fever, which can be linked to significant toxemia (toxic scarlet fever) and localized, hematogenous dissemination of the organism (septic scarlet fever)^[11].

Complications of scarlet fever are local and systemic in nature. Peritonsillar and retropharyngeal abscesses are the local complications. Systemic complications are acute rheumatic fever, meningitis, glomerulonephritis, pneumonia, and endocarditis. Rarely, scarlet fever can cause the development of splenomegaly, hepatitis, or gallbladder hydrops^[3]. No complications were observed because of the infection in our case.

Our patient also had a gluteal abscess, which was dealt with incision and drainage. *Staphylococcus aureus* was isolated in the drained purulent material when subjected to culture and sensitivity testing. There are also reports of staphylococcal scarlet fever in the literature, which is thought to be a mild form of SSSS or TSS^[12]. In our case, exanthem with enanthema and tongue involvement (hypertrophied papillae) point toward streptococcal scarlet fever because a strawberry tongue is seen with streptococcal but not staphylococcal scarlet fever^[13].

Diagnosis depends on several factors, including a complete history of all clinical symptoms before exanthem, a positive family history, the location and progression of the lesions, a history of systemic medication, and the child and their caretakers' recent travel history^[14-17].

A thorough medical history, along with a distinctive clinical appearance, is typically used to make a diagnosis of scarlet fever diagnosis. A culture of the throat swab should be performed in order to confirm the diagnosis^[15,18]. Rapid antigen tests that are more convenient and faster have high specificity—95% or more. Since the sensitivity of the culture is superior to that of the rapid antigen tests, it is recommended to confirm a negative rapid antigen test result in children and adolescents with a throat culture^[19]. Since the body takes two to three weeks to produce the antibodies against a streptococcal infection (antistreptolysin O and anti-deoxyribonuclease B), serological testing, where the antibodies against a streptococcal infection are detected, does not help in diagnosing current scarlet fever but can be performed when assessing a person with complications from a previous streptococcal infection^[20].

Initiation of antimicrobial therapy at the earliest time is crucial in scarlet fever because it shortens the duration of the infection and helps to avoid complications. Since an individual loses their contagiousness after receiving treatment after 24 hours, it prevents disease transmission among the pediatric population.^[15,18] Beta-lactam antibiotics are the recommended treatment for GAS infection because of their safety in children with clinical and cost effectiveness^[19]. Penicillin or amoxicillin, in appropriate dosages and regimens, continue to be the first-choice antibiotic for treating GAS infections; they appear to be more efficacious than cephalosporins and macrolides. If the patient is allergic to penicillin, clindamycin or a first-generation cephalosporin may be administered^[15].

Oral Amoxicillin clavulanate along with symptomatic treatment was given in our patient, to which he responded well with the resolution of symptoms in 1 week.

IVIG is the other modality used in patients with complications associated with scarlet fever or in patients with concomitant toxic shock syndrome because of a lack of specific antitoxic immunity^[21].

Most of the patients who receive timely therapeutic intervention have excellent outcomes. Resolution is usually seen in 3-6 days, though skin symptoms may require 14-21 days to subside^[22]. There was a resolution of both skin and mucosal features in a week with no untoward sequelae in our case.

CONCLUSION

Scarlet fever is a bacterial infection caused by *Streptococcus pyogenes*, with clinical presentation ranging from mild to severe. Though we encountered a gluteal abscess due to staphylococcal origin, we ruled out staphylococcal scarlet fever from the presence of enanthema and strawberry tongue and throat culture showing a growth of *streptococcus pyogenes*. Early detection and management of scarlet fever are essential to prevent local and systemic complications.

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